

A hierarchical simulation-based push planner for autonomous recovery in navigation blocked scenarios of mobile robots

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ABSTRACT

Mobile robotic platforms that are expected to be engaged in applications domains characterized by unstructured terrains and environment settings will unavoidably face mobility constraints that may not be overcome by classical navigation planning and obstacle avoidance/negotiation tools. Endowing these robots with additional skills, which enable them to interact and manipulate obstacles blocking their pathway, will significantly enhance their ability to deal with such conditions, permitting them to perform their mission more robustly when encountering such unstructured and cluttered scenes. This paper proposes a novel hierarchical simulation-based push planner framework that searches for a sequence of pushing actions to move obstacles toward a planned goal position. This aims at overcoming obstacle challenges that block the navigation of the robot toward a target location and, therefore, can lead to the failure of the navigation plan and the overall mission of the robot. The planned pushing actions enable the robot to relocate objects in the scene avoiding obstacles and considering environmental constraints identified by an elevation or an occupancy map. The online simulations of the pushing actions are carried out by exploiting the Mujoco physics engine. The framework was validated in the Gazebo simulation environment and in real platforms such as the hybrid wheeled-legged robot CENTAURO and the mobile cobot RELAX.

1. Introduction

The application of robotics in unstructured environments demands robotic systems that are capable of dealing in a robust manner with significant mobility and navigation challenges posed by the uncertainty of such workspaces. While capabilities such as obstacle detection, avoidance, or crossing can be most times very effective, conditions may arise in which the avoidance or the negotiation of the obstacles is not possible due to the limited available space around the obstacles as well as due to mobility limitation of the robotic platform. In such scenarios, the introduction of an additional capability of the robot to interact, manipulate, and eventually relocate obstacles that are preventing the robot from reaching its target location, can be greatly beneficial. This additional feature increases the robustness of the robot's operation and its autonomy level, enabling the robot to autonomously overcome navigation failures and complete critical missions that, otherwise, will have to be abandoned.

The work presented in this paper proposes a push planner framework to extend the autonomous capabilities of floating-based robots enabling such mobile robotic platforms to autonomously plan for a sequence of pushing actions, rearranging the objects' configuration in

the space. Our approach leverages a Behavior Tree (BT) [1] to control the execution of the framework, react autonomously to errors and inaccuracies, and replan from the newly discovered location of the object. This enables to overcome the strong dependency on the object's pose accuracy, improving the framework's robustness.

The core of the proposed push planner framework is implemented as a hierarchical simulation-based architecture with a division into global and local planners. The global planners, based on a constrained version of the Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (RRT) [2], plan for a sequence of collision-free object poses from the starting position of the object to the planned target one. On the other hand, the local planner is responsible for planning the robot movements and pushing actions, simulating them in parallel using the Mujoco simulator [3] to connect the sampled nodes of the global planner to the tree built. The possibility to simulate pushing actions allows abstracting from the need for a mathematical model of the robotic platform, allowing the framework to be easily adapted to different robots without the need to change its implementation.

The main contributions of this work include the following:

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- The definition of a constrained hierarchical push planner framework based on parallelized simulation steps;
- The consideration of environmental data for collision-free objects poses and robot movements;
- The adaptation of the planning pushes based on the kinematics and the end-effectors of the platform considered;
- The autonomous selection of the object/obstacle to push and the estimation of its candidate target position to solve the task;
- The extensive validation of the proposed push planner in simulation and experimentally with two robotic platforms, the mobile platform RELAX [4] and the wheeled-legged robot CEN-TAURO [5], considering complex environments where the navigation of the robots is prevented by the obstacles.

2. Related works

Object manipulation is an interesting and well-studied topic in robotics that finds application in various tasks, such as grasping or using a tool. When navigating within cluttered and unstructured environments, a robot may be required to remove some elements of the scene to clear the path toward its target location. In the literature, several methods have been exploited to manipulate objects, mainly focusing on the use of robotic hands to accomplish the task. However, two main strategies have been explored when there is the need to move one object to a target position. The first one consists of grasping the object and moving it to another position in the space. This approach has been widely used in robotics to interact with objects of different natures. Few examples of grasping applications are [6–8]. In this approach, the grasping action depends on an appropriate object pose estimation [9], the type of end-effector used, as well as a grasp planner to provide the most suitable hand configuration as in [10] and [11].

The other possible way to achieve the desired task involves the use of graspless manipulation [12,13], consisting of pushing, tumbling, or sliding the object to move it to the target position without requiring a specific end-effector to be used.

2.1. Graspless manipulation

Graspless manipulation is particularly useful when the robot has to deal with big or heavy objects that cannot be grasped and lifted or when the robotic platform does not have the necessary capacity to perform grasping in general, as for mobile platforms that are not embedded with arms and end-effectors. Graspless manipulation is a challenging problem that requires accurate planning considering contact points and physics. In [14] is presented a study of pushing literature involving different possibilities ranging from pure analytical methods to simulators and data-driven ones. Most of the listed methods work in a planar world, like in [15], which describes a planner for multi-contact non-prehensile manipulation. Other works were focused on planar pushing as [16] or [17]. The first describes a method to perform object placement on a table surface where pushing is used when there is insufficient space for direct placement, demonstrating the results only in simulations. The latter presents preliminary work on path generation and push planning on a 2D grid, where the push planner module uses the predicted object motions. Also for this work, the results are shown only in simulation, without using an actual robotic platform.

An additional work is [18], which proposes a method for handling and pushing boxes with unmanned guided vehicles, describing strategic points with a topological map and planning on the graph using Dijkstra's algorithm. Nevertheless, here, there is only the possibility of moving an object continuously, which cannot be done with legged robotic platforms, and only simulations are presented. Moreover, no occlusions in the environment are considered. Similarly, [19] addresses unknown object delivery with a mobile base, adding environment considerations.

2.2. Push planners in 3D

To generalize and consider changes in the orientation of the objects during the planning part, we restricted our focus to algorithms dealing with 3D worlds, and that were designed to perform path planning. These drastically reduced the number of works proposed in the field of graspless manipulation. In particular, in [20] is presented an analytical method to perform path planning via pushing actions, but, to work correctly, the analytical method requires extreme accuracy in the description of the object, contacts, and friction parameters to analytically compute the needed measurements, making it complex to adapt to different objects and robotic platforms.

In [21], a method is proposed in which a manipulator has to push an object to the workspace of a second arm. Initially, the object is pushed to understand its properties by simulating the effect of a force with various parameters with the Bullet¹ physics engine, identifying the model parameters that match the visual observation. This approach shows promising results, however, it is not suitable for our objective since one of the requirements is to plan more complex trajectories even in cluttered environments.

In [22], a two-level framework is developed to plan pushing actions, simulating them in the PhysX² environment where a robotic arm is used to tilt an L-shape object on a free table surface.

Similarly to these last two works, [23] proposes PokeRRT demonstrating poking capabilities with a robotic arm. This work is limited to fixed-base manipulators, dealing with objects of small dimensions, weight, and poking space, given by the manipulator's reachable space.

To the author's knowledge, no pushing frameworks have been proposed in the past years that can be effortlessly applied to different varieties of floating-base robots, from legged robots to mobile platforms. In particular, focusing on increasing the robot's autonomous capabilities to navigate in constrained scenarios that may have barriers that prevent the navigation, but also obstacles that limit the working area of the robot and the object being pushed to complete the assigned task. In addition, no reasoning capabilities have been identified in the previous works to address the fully autonomous selection of the objects to be pushed, often requiring human in the loop.

The approach we propose in this paper shows noticeable improvements in the robot's reasoning capabilities, enabling the robot to autonomously select the objects to push, together with their desired target location. Then, according to the platform's kinematics, a sequence of pushing actions is planned and executed to complete the task. In the next sections, we present the framework components used to process the environment and search for a sequence of pushing actions.

3. Push planner framework

The push planner framework proposed in this paper is defined by different software components (implemented as ROS nodes) that communicate with each other through ROS topics, services, and actions. A visual representation of the main components implemented and how they communicate with each other is shown in Fig. 1, where the cloud represents external elements/frameworks, such as the locomotion and the object segmentation ones. Rectangles are used to describe software components, and the circle is used for hardware elements like the cameras and the robot.

In the following subsections, such components are explained in more detail, starting from the ones used to process and acquire the map. However, to ensure clarity, a brief outline of the execution order for the proposed framework is provided here. First of all, a target location to be reached by the robot is provided by the operator and acquired by the Push Manager. This is the only input required by the operator

¹ <https://pybullet.org>

² <https://developer.nvidia.com/physx-sdk>

Fig. 1. Graphical representation of the implemented framework's components and their interaction.

which, in future applications, can also be provided by external higher-level modules. Then, the Push Manager asks the locomotion framework if a feasible locomotion plan is available for the robot to reach the desired target pose. In the case that no solution can be found, the Push Planner is triggered, starting the actual planning part. The goal is to find a sequence of pushing actions to rearrange the objects in the environment and create a new passage for the robot. The Push Planner starts by acquiring and processing the map of the environment and then communicates with the Plan Target Pose component to select the most suitable object to push, together with its candidate pose in the space. At this point, the actual planning part starts searching for a sequence of pushing actions that solve the task. Once a solution is found, it is acquired by the Push Manager and sent to the Push Executor one pushing action at a time to be executed on the robot.

More details on the single components are given in the following sections.

3.1. Map processing and target estimation

The first described components are the ones used to acquire the map of the environment, process it, and select the best object to push to complete the assigned task.

3.1.1. Map acquisition

To plan robot movements and collision-free pushes, it is required to acquire information from the environment about the terrain composition. The Map Acquisition module aims to build a representation of the environment in the form of an occupancy map, containing information on whether a certain area is occupied by an object or not. In particular, the acquisition process is performed with the ROS package *gmapping* [24] for the cobot using the 2D LiDARs available. While for CENTAURO, we extracted the point cloud of the scene through the RGB-D camera and processed it to obtain an elevation map using [25]. From the elevation map, we then generate a 2D occupancy map, marking as obstacles the elements higher than the ground. Without loss of generality or changes in the performances, the mapping process can be performed both online while the robot is moving or by loading a pre-saved map of the environment. In Figs. 2A–B are shown the top view of a Gazebo simulation environment and the corresponding occupancy grid, where in black are marked as occupied the static obstacles of the scene. The occupancy map is published at 5 Hz in the case of the RELAX robot and at 2 Hz in the case of CENTAURO.

3.1.2. Plan Target Pose

Once the occupancy map is acquired, the Push Planner triggers the Plan Target Pose module. Its task is to consider all the movable objects and select the one to push, together with the candidate target position that this object will have to reach, if not explicitly specified by the user. The Plan Target Pose component takes as input the occupancy map of the environment, the actual position of the robot, the dimension and pose of the movable objects, and the target pose that the robot has to reach. The first step consists of processing the occupancy map. In particular, the occupied areas of the map are inflated to avoid collisions with the elements of the environment. At this point, if a static map of the scene is being used, the additional movable objects are added to the map and marked as obstacles, to avoid colliding with them. Otherwise, in the case of online mapping, the information on the movable obstacles is already captured by the sensors and embedded in the map. The result of this first processing part is shown in Fig. 2C. Then, the line connecting the current robot position and its target is inflated, based on the dimension of the robot as shown in Fig. 2D. This avoids pushing the object to a position close to the area that will be traversed to reach the target position, helping to reduce the possibility of invalidating future navigation plans. Now, the Plan Target Pose module defines which object the robot should push to navigate to the target position by evaluating a complexity index for each movable object with the weighted sum expressed below:

$$Cost = D_p \cdot K_p + D_s \cdot K_s + D_t \cdot K_t + S \cdot K_{dim} + M \cdot K_M$$

where D_p is the minimum squared distance between the object and the line connecting the starting and target position of the robot, D_s and D_t represent the distance between the object and the starting and target position of the robot, S is the sum of the 3 dimensions of the object, while M is its mass. The gains K_x are used to define how to score the different quantities. The object with the smallest cost is selected as the candidate one. Moreover, in case of planning failures or if the previous pushing actions did not move the object because it was stuck or heavier than estimated, an additional cost is added. This helps dealing with errors in the object's parameters or with the object's movement being too limited by the environment. In this way, the planner can try to push a different object that can solve the task or free the constrained area, without the need to continue considering the same object and getting stuck. Once the object has been selected, then $C = 10000$ candidate poses of the object are randomly sampled, as simplified in Fig. 2E, discarding the ones overlapping with occupied areas in the map, which would correspond to collisions with the environment. Finally, among the valid ones, it is selected and used as the final target position for the candidate object the pose closest to the starting position of the object to reduce the overall movement required, Fig. 2F. The average time

Fig. 2. Processing of the occupancy map and searching for the object to push, together with the sampling of its candidate target position.

to perform the map processing and the candidate object selection is 163.0 ms.

If the task of the robot is to move an object to a specific area and not to overcome navigation failures, then the target position of the robot will not be considered for the cost evaluation.

Once the map has been processed and the candidate object selected, the last step is to mark as free the occupancy grid in the area currently occupied by the candidate object selected to be pushed since this object cannot collide with itself. This map will be used as input by the planner to check collisions with the environment for both the robot and the candidate object.

3.2. Planning and execution details

This section introduces the actual planning part, exploiting its inner mechanisms and better describing the overall execution of the framework. Specifically, we are going to present and highlight the characteristics of the Push Planner, Push Executor, and Push Manager, together with the other components involved in the planning phase. The Push Planner component, visually represented in Fig. 3, is the one responsible for the search of a sequence of pushing actions and was designed to have a hierarchical structure. The main elements of the Push Planner component are the Top Global Planner, Global Planner, and Local Planner. The task of the two global planners is to sample the poses of the candidate object on the map, avoiding collisions to connect it to the target pose estimated. The local planner, on the other hand, searches for a sequence of pushing actions and robot movements to move the object to the new pose sampled by the global planner. The

local planner achieves its task by communicating also with additional modules, the Inverse Kinematic (IK) Server and the Physics Simulators.

3.2.1. Global planner

The global planner presented here is based on the RRT algorithm and has the goal of connecting the starting position of the object to the target one acquired by the Plan Target Pose module, sampling poses in a random way. In this global stage, the nodes of the RRT contain information about the pose of the candidate object only, with respect to a fixed global frame.

RRT is a widely used technique for path planning that easily handles problems with obstacles, high dimensional space, and differential constraints. With respect to the classical RRT, we added different constraints to the randomness of the nodes. In particular, we changed the probability distribution function used for the search from a uniform distribution to a Gaussian one in which the mean is defined as the node in the tree that is the closest to the goal. This helps avoid searching intensively around positions far from the interested point, arriving much faster to the goal. In this way, we decrease the computational time and the possibility to generate much longer solutions.

In addition, to speed up the planner and limit the randomness of the RRT, we introduced a constraint to discard random nodes that are too far or too close from each other, setting a maximum and minimum distance to 0.60 m and 0.20 m for RELAX and 0.45 m and 0.135 m for CENTAURO due to the kinematic of the legs. In this way, a lower number of iterations of the local planner will be needed to connect or reject the new random node sampled by the RRT.

Fig. 3. Components of the hierarchical pushing architecture with two sequential global planners, one local planner, and IK and simulation servers used during the local planning steps.

Fig. 4. Comparison between the variants of the RRT searches considering Gaussian and Uniform distributions with constrained or unconstrained distance between the nodes in the tree. (A) shows the planning time to find a solution, (B) the global nodes explored to find a solution.

A comparison among these variants in terms of time and nodes explored is reported in Fig. 4 where the data of 10 runs for each category is averaged. Here we used the RELAX platform and requested the robot to push a wooden box for 8.0m. The object had a mass of 2.5 kg and a dimension of 0.5 m × 1.0 m × 0.5 m. At this step, no local planner was used, the comparison involved only the global planner with different implementation details. The rest of the parameters, including the map, starting pose, and target pose, remained constant for this comparison. The difference between the two Gaussian versions is minor in these tests since the Gaussian allows sampling nodes close to the tree, so it is unlikely to consider “far” nodes even in the unbounded case.

Another feature we added to the planner is the possibility of considering environmental information. In particular, at the beginning of the search, the planner acquires the occupancy map and uses it to validate the objects’ poses randomly sampled. In more detail, the validation process includes the random sampling of the RRT node, the checking of the distance constraints, and finally the checking of collisions with the occupied areas of the map. If a check is violated, the node is discarded and a new iteration of the global plan starts, sampling a new node. Otherwise, if the pose is valid, the local planner is invoked to connect the new sampled node with the global tree.

With the introduction of constrained environments, as in the case of rooms and corridors, we noticed that using static parameters for the Gaussian distribution resulted in longer planning time. In fact, in these scenarios, the object is supposed to move further from the goal to be able to reach the entrance of the room, as shown in Fig. 5. For such a reason, the global planner was modified to have dynamic changes in the standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution. Specifically, if after randomly sampling X valid object poses, no pose is found that is closer to the target than any of the existing nodes in the tree, the standard deviation is increased to encourage a broader exploration of the search space.

To avoid waiting extensive time for a solution, we set a maximum number of global steps to 2000 for RELAX and 500 for CENTAURO.

3.2.2. Local planner

The local planner is responsible for connecting the RRT nodes through a sequence of randomly sampled pushing actions and for planning robot movements to adapt the robot’s configuration to the scene while pushing. The local planner starts selecting the most suitable modality to push an object, taking into account the robot configuration, the list of available end-effectors, the dimension of the object, and the direction in which the object needs to be moved. In particular, if, along

Fig. 5. Behavior of the Gaussian sampling with fixed (A) and dynamic (B) standard deviation.

Fig. 6. Examples of the pushing primitives available for the CENTAURO robot (left) and for the RELAX platform (right).

the pushing direction, the object is bigger than a threshold (specified by the robot type), then the object is pushed with the entire body, driving the robot toward the object. On the other hand, if the object is smaller, a single leg is used in the case of a legged robot. Moreover, there is still the possibility to enable pushing with the arms, in case of obstacles that exceed a certain elevation, which is a parameter that depends on the robotic platform considered. This can also have the effect of tilting the object, making it easier to be pushed in the next actions, using the lower body of the robot. Visual examples of the available pushing actions for both the CENTAURO and RELAX can be seen in Fig. 6. In the case of failing during the sampling of the actions for one modality, the sampling procedure tries to find a valid pushing action with the other end-effectors/modalities available.

Once the desired pushing mode is selected, to reduce the issues related to the robot configuration and its stability, especially when pushing with legs or arms, the local planner plans a movement of the robot toward the object. In this way, the robot is close to the object,

limiting the possibilities of singular configurations and improving stability by moving the end-effector to a smaller quantity. In addition, in the case of legged robots, it is planned a reshape of the support polygon to adapt it to the environment. At this point, the planner is ready to randomly sample N cartesian poses for the end-effector corresponding to the pushing action. The next step is to send the target positions associated with the selected end-effector to the IK Server to obtain the joint trajectory to perform the push. During the sampling process, the actions passing through the CoM of the object are favored. This has the objective of moving the object toward the goal, and improving the control of the orientation.

Finally, each sampled action is simulated within the Mujoco simulation environment, providing as output the final pose of the object after the application of the pushing action considered. Once all the random actions have been tested, only the one that moves the object closer to the target position is kept, then the planner starts from this new position and iterates for N_{local} times. If the distance between the real object position and the target position is below a certain threshold (x_{dist}

= 0.06 m) the local planner succeeded and its execution is stopped. The result is a sequence of pushing actions and robot movements that is returned to the global planner and added to the sampled node of the tree, enriching the information carried in the tree. Otherwise, the sequence of actions is discarded.

The choice of simulating the pushing actions is derived from the desire to abstract from mathematical models that are difficult to adapt to different robotic platforms. While, inside the simulation environment to consider a different robotic platform it is only required to change the URDF file of the robot.

3.2.3. IK server

To reduce the differences between the real robot movements and the simulated one, we decided to add an IK Server, built using our cartesian controller, CartesIO [26]. This module has the objective of finding the joint trajectory that brings the robot to the configuration in which the end-effector is in the position planned by the local planner. The trajectory is then stored for the duration of a single search and associated with the resulting push action sampled. This allows replicating on the robot the exact movement of the simulation environment, without the need to compute the IK for a second time, reducing the computational time required and the error between the real robot's movement and the simulated one. However, this feature can be disabled through a configuration to reduce memory consumption. In this case, only the target pose of the end-effector will be stored and the IK will have to be run in the execution step to obtain the reference joint trajectory. The time required by the IK Server to provide the joint trajectory is on average 9.88 ms.

3.2.4. Physics simulator server

The proposed implementation of the planner takes advantage of a physics simulator to estimate the results of pushing actions. Here we decided to use Mujoco since it has already been used for robotics applications in terms of simulation but also learning as in [27] and [27]. Each server exposes a service to simulate the pushing action, taking as input the object properties (size and mass) and its starting pose, the starting robot configuration, and the joint trajectory to be followed to execute the pushing action. The result sent back is the final position of the object. To speed up the simulation and reduce the computational cost, we simplified the meshes of the robot that are not involved in the pushing action and enabled check for contacts only among the end effectors, the object to be pushed, and the floor. In addition, after executing a pushing action on the real robot, to improve the modeling of the physical parameters in the simulation environment, these are adjusted by comparing the planned position of the object to the actual one.

3.2.5. Push manager

To manage and monitor the correct execution of the framework, we designed the Behavior Tree (BT) shown in Fig. 7. The BT ticks the nodes from the left to the right, checking with the action *DriveToPos* if the robot can navigate to the target location querying the navigation framework. If no navigation plan is found, the BT invokes the push planner and waits for a sequence of pushing actions. Once the sequence is found, the BT acquires it through the action *AcquirePlan* and sends it to the robot to be executed, one action at a time. When executing a pushing action, the Push Manager checks if a valid plan was collected with the condition *PlanCollected* and verifies if the robot is currently pushing an object with the action *IsPushing*. In case of *FAILURE*, the robot is not pushing an object, and the Push Manager checks if the actual position of the object is close to the planned one with the condition *ValidDistance*, to avoid pushing an object that is far from the planned position. If the distance is below a set threshold, the Push Manager requests the robot to drive to the planned position with the action *DriveToPos* and executes the pushing action with *ExecuteNextPush*. Otherwise, if the *ValidDistance* check fails, it means that the current

position of the object is too far from the planned one and so the next pushing action cannot be executed. In this case, a new request to the push planner is sent, considering the updated object's position.

After completing a pushing action, if the task of the robot is to navigate to a target pose, the Push Manager asks the locomotion module if the robot is now able to reach the target location to avoid pushing continuously if the way is clear enough for the robot to proceed with the locomotion. On the other hand, if the robot is requested to push the object in a specific position, then this check is skipped and the execution goes on until the object reaches the desired pose or area in the space.

One important thing to notice is that, with the possibility of updating the plan in case of failures, it is not strictly required to have a perfect model of the object and friction parameters. The more correct your model is, the more correct the solution will be, requiring fewer replannings and saving time in the execution. However, a rough estimation of the parameters will not prevent the robot from completing the task assigned, but more calls to the push planner will be needed due to the misalignment between the real world and the Mujoco simulation.

3.2.6. Top global planner

Further to the local and global planner structure defined above, we also introduced an additional instance of the global planner on top of them. The implementation is the same as described in Section 3.2.1 with differences in the parameters and without using the local planner. In more detail, we set a maximum and minimum distance between nodes to 0.20m and 0.05m, maximum numbers of nodes explored 5000 and we decreased the standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution. This planner has the objective of finding a sequence of valid poses of the object, between the current position of the object and the target candidate one in a few milliseconds, in average 15 ms. Then, the global planner has to find a solution not to the final target position, but to a pose, extracted from this top global plan, at a maximum distance of 1.25 m. The logic behind this additional planner is to break the planning sequence into smaller pieces. Without this step, the planning time strongly depends on the distance between the starting and target position of the object resulting in longer planning time for longer distances. With this additional feature, the planning time remains bounded and the robot can start to move without the need to plan for the entire sequence of pushing actions. Fig. 8 shows the planning time with respect to the distance to the target, with and without the top global planner. The tests were made in simulation, pushing a 2.5 kg box with the RELAX platform for 8 m.

3.2.7. Push Executor

Once the Push Manager has verified the validity of the object's pose by checking its actual position with respect to the planned one, it sends the pushing action to be performed to the Push Executor. This component manages the robot's motion through our control framework CartesIO [26] and the Xbot2 middleware [28]. In addition, during the pushing actions, the force exerted by the end-effector on the object is monitored through a force estimator. The force is evaluated from the torque reads in the joints of the kinematic chain of the end effector. If the estimated force overcomes a threshold, the pushing action is suspended to avoid stressing or damaging the actuators.

4. Experiments and results

To demonstrate the validity and adaptability of the proposed framework, we run experiments with two robotic platforms. We used the CENTAURO robot, which has four 5-DoFs legs ending in 360° steerable wheels and a humanoid upper body, and the mobile robot RELAX, a non-holonomic base equipped with a 6-DoFs robotic arm on top of it.

In this Section, we first illustrate preliminary tests performed to tune the parameters involved in the simulation environment. Then we focus on the experiments in which the robot has to get to locations

Fig. 7. Behavior Tree designed to manage the push planner, execute the pushing actions, and communicate with the locomotion system.

Fig. 8. Comparison of planning time with and without the additional global planner on top of the framework.

that cannot be reached via navigation, so the push planner is invoked to relocate the obstacles and create new pathways to the navigation target. In addition to this, we demonstrate that the framework can also target tasks where the robot is required to push objects in specific areas of the environment, avoiding obstacles.

All the simulation experiments were carried out on a PC embedded with 16 GB of RAM, an Intel i7-10700, and an NVIDIA T600 graphic card. Thanks to the modularity of the framework, we were able to use the hybrid locomotion framework proposed and tested in [29] for the CENTAURO robot, while for the RELAX platform, the ROS Navigation Stack was exploited [30].

4.1. Simulators tuning

To match the push simulation with the real one we started experimentally tuning the parameters involved like lateral, spinning, and rolling friction, linear and angular damping as well as the time step of

the simulation and control gains. The Gazebo environment was tuned to represent realistic collisions, then we tuned Mujoco according to Gazebo.

Due to the complexity of the considered robot and the different contacts involved in a single simulation, we needed to use a small value for the timestep, set to $t_s = 0.0007$ s, to avoid unrealistic collisions. This implies a higher computational time needed for a single execution, bringing us to perform parallel simulations. We defined N_{local} physics simulator servers that run in parallel, exposing a service to simulate a single pushing action. In this way, all the N_{local} sampled actions can be tested simultaneously, reducing the simulation time by a factor that is experimentally in the range $[0.5 * N_{local}, N_{local}]$.

To evaluate and tune the simulation environment, we run several tests with different parameters and parallelization numbers. We tried to keep the time step at the highest possible without damaging the accuracy of the push. Fig. 9 shows how the time step and the number of parallel simulators affect the simulation time. As can be seen, the

Fig. 9. (A) Comparison of the simulation time by varying the number of parallel simulators with Mujoco. (B) Changes of simulation timestep with RELAX and CENTAURO robots.

time for simulating $N = 10$ actions in parallel is one and a half the time needed to test a single action in the serial case ($N = 1$). In our tests, we decided to use $N = 6$ for the RELAX platform and $N = 4$ for the CENTAURO robot, to avoid stressing too much the embedded computer's resources. The tests described above were carried out considering an object of dimensions $1.0 \times 0.5 \times 0.5$ m, and a mass of 1 kg.

Subsequently, we performed several tests randomly selecting the dimension and weight of the objects to check the accuracy and further tune the parameters involved, reducing the mismatch between the Gazebo simulation environment and Mujoco. In these preliminary tests, the robot was supposed to move an object for 1.5 m in an empty area. Due to the absence of objects in the scene, the planner requires less time to find a solution because there is no need to iterate on the map to find collision-free poses, reshaping the support polygon, and trajectories. In more detail, in the Mujoco environment, we set for all the objects the anisotropic tangential friction of the *pair* attributes to 0.65 and the sliding friction of the *geometries* to 0.80. Then, we modified the anisotropic tangential friction between the wheels and the ground to 1.0 and the one between the object and the ground to 0.565. Where *geometries* represent the parts of a body and *pair* the collision between two specified geometries. In the Gazebo simulator, we set μ , μ_2 , and the torsional friction equal to 0.6.

4.2. Autonomous escape from closed environments

Once we tested the framework in a simple environment, we started to make the environment more complex by adding obstacles to limit the working area. Here the planner has to take into account the occupancy map and discard the poses that would create a collision between the object and the environment but also between the robot and the environment. Now the planning time increases due to the checks on the map and the possibility of performing the reshape of the support polygon, in the case of a legged robot.

Figs. 10.1 and 10.2 show two of the examples of constrained environments used in the simulation with the RELAX robot. The robot is placed in a warehouse scenario in which the access to the corridors and rooms is blocked by the movable obstacles, highlighted in red. These correspond to rectangular wooden boxes, wooden platforms, and pallets with different dimensions, configurations, and masses (between 1 and 20 kg). The goal of the task was to reach the red flags in the image. In the beginning, the navigation framework is not able to provide a solution due to the objects blocking the way, so the push planner is invoked. The complexity indices are evaluated, selecting as a candidate

the more appropriate object to push. Then, the robot starts to push the object until the occupancy map becomes free enough to reach the goal via navigation. In both scenarios, the robot is requested to reach more targets, interacting with different objects based on the position of the robot and the next navigation target. The only inputs required are the target positions to be reached. Then the selection of the object to be pushed, together with the pushing actions, is executed automatically. It has to be noted that, when moving to the last target of 10.2, the robot will push the object with the arm to tilt it and simplify the next pushing actions which will be performed with the base.

4.3. Hybrid planner integration

The proposed push planner also finds application as a recovery method for the hybrid navigation of wheeled-legged robots like the CENTAURO robot. In particular, we considered different scenarios where the robot is requested to navigate through a room as in Fig. 10.11. However, in this case, the navigation planner is not able to find a solution due to the width of the bricks, the inflation considered around them, and the holes on them, which makes the area untraversable. For this reason, the push planner is invoked to push the bricks and open a path that can be used by the robot to navigate. Once the bricks are moved, the navigation planner can find a solution and the robot navigates to the assigned target location.

4.4. Pushing to targeted areas

Although the main focus of the framework is to unstuck the robot during a navigation task when the robot is blocked due to environmental constraints and obstacles, it is important to notice that the push planner can also be used as a standalone module to push objects to a final goal or a selected area. Few examples of this can be shown in Figs. 10.3, 10.4 and 10.10, where the robot has to move the boxes in the corresponding colored zones. The target pose of the objects to be pushed is randomly sampled inside the desired areas while the order of pushing is selected based on the complexity indices. To test and validate this feature, we tested the push planner requesting the robot to push 2 or 3 objects of varying dimensions and mass to specific areas in the environment. The environments considered here were empty and cluttered rooms, with objects that required obstacle avoidance and support polygon adaptation.

Fig. 10. Environments considered for validation. (1) and (2) RELAX navigating to the red flags. (3) and (4) RELAX pushing objects to target areas. (5)–(8) experimental trials with scenarios of navigation while objects are blocking the passage. (9) experimental trials involving pushing actions in an area with obstacles. (10) CENTAURO pushing objects to target areas. (11) CENTAURO navigating and pushing objects. (12) Experimental tests with CENTAURO pushing objects in target areas.

4.5. Real robot experiments

After testing the framework in simulation, we further validated it on real robotic platforms. To obtain the position of the objects with respect to the robot in these experiments we used Aruco Markers, since object segmentation is not the focus of this paper.

With the RELAX platform, we run experiments similar to the simulated ones, where the robot has to navigate to a target position as in Fig. 10.5–Fig. 10.8 but also to push an object in a defined area avoiding obstacles like in Fig. 10.9. Here we placed wooden platforms to resemble rooms and corridors with the objective of traversing the scene and reaching the red flags. The framework demonstrated good

Table 1
Results from the trials in simulation and on the real robots with different environments. Mean [standard deviation].

Scene N	Total pushes	Exec. time [s]	Plan time [s]	Push error [m]	Pushed distance [m]	Success local	Success planner	Success rate
SIMULATION TESTS: RELAX								
1	5.1 [0.6]	224.2 [35.0]	4.7 [14.3]	0.08 [0.08]	1.37 [0.30]	0.86 [0.24]	0.98 [0.01]	10/10
2	13.8 [2.2]	577.7 [82.3]	6.4 [17.2]	0.11 [0.14]	2.90 [0.56]	0.76 [0.28]	0.92 [0.03]	9/10
3	24.4 [2.8]	577.9 [58.0]	1.1 [3.3]	0.06 [0.05]	7.01 [0.78]	0.93 [0.12]	1.0 [0.0]	10/10
4	12.3 [3.1]	332.7 [79.8]	3.21 [8.9]	0.06 [0.05]	3.56 [0.54]	0.80 [0.23]	0.96 [0.04]	10/10
REAL TESTS: RELAX								
5	5.5 [0.6]	182.5 [22.1]	3.3 [7.8]	0.07 [0.04]	2.02 [0.19]	0.87 [0.17]	0.85 [0.12]	5/5
6	2.5 [0.6]	119.5 [39.3]	3.3 [2.3]	0.08 [0.03]	0.94 [0.32]	0.62 [0.30]	0.27 [0.22]	5/5
7	3.0 [0.0]	170.8 [57.5]	8.6 [13.3]	0.08 [0.03]	1.05 [0.17]	0.71 [0.33]	0.48 [0.02]	5/5
8	8.7 [1.5]	298.7 [66.6]	5.1 [10.3]	0.09 [0.5]	3.07 [0.15]	0.71 [0.33]	0.53 [0.03]	3/5
9	5.5 [1.7]	170.3 [54]	0.7 [0.6]	0.11 [0.13]	1.72 [0.27]	0.97 [0.09]	1.0 [0.0]	5/5
SIMULATION TESTS: CENTAURO								
10	17.0 [1.4]	658.0 [60.71]	5.8 [15.0]	0.08 [0.04]	3.37 [0.39]	0.88 [0.21]	0.99 [0.01]	5/5
11	2.4 [0.5]	171.0 [15.7]	10.2 [14.9]	0.06 [0.03]	0.30 [0.10]	0.35 [0.38]	0.62 [0.23]	5/5
REAL TESTS: CENTAURO								
12	8.4 [1.8]	425.4 [78.4]	8.9 [10.9]	0.06 [0.05]	1.32 [0.17]	0.50 [0.38]	0.87 [0.09]	8/10

results and robustness, in fact, even in the case in which the marker was not recognized (and therefore the object position was not updated), the robot continued to push, having a larger error, until the marker was visualized. At this point, the actual pose of the object is kept into account and the correct execution goes on, without the need to stop the robot or terminate the execution.

For the CENTAURO robot, we considered a scenario in which the robot has to push a wooden box to a selected area while avoiding the bricks in the scene as in Fig. 10.12. Due to the camera orientation, the robot cannot see the marker after the pushing action, so it was required the addition of a navigation step to move the robot backward (about 0.30 m) after every push so the robot could see the object again but also to update the elevation map after the change in the environment. This increases the execution time but further demonstrates the full integration with the hybrid navigation planner.

Table 1 presents the results of the experiments, corresponding to Fig. 10, showing the total number of pushes executed in the entire run, the execution and planning time, the error in the pushing actions and the overall distance pushed. In addition, the success rate of the push planner in finding a solution, the success rate of the local planner's steps to connect two RRT nodes, and the rate of success of the experiments are listed. The failures of the push planner are related to the hardly constrained scenario when the robot has to move a box inside a corridor/room, resulting in no sampling actions to simulate because of the collision between the environment and the robot. In the case of CENTAURO, the planning failures are mainly related to the slow updates of the map after moving the object. However, thanks to the randomness of the RRT, if no solution is found, the next iteration will sample different nodes, updating the map with the latest sensor's data, and allowing the planner to find different paths to the goal. The failed experiments for the real CENTAURO robot were related to hardware issues that forced to stop the execution, even if a feasible solution was found. It has to be noted that, in both simulation and, especially, real environments, part of the error in the result of the pushes is given by the use of floating base robots. In fact, the navigation has a tolerance in the target pose to avoid oscillations. Thus, starting with a small error in the position and orientation before pushing the object can result in a different pushing direction or rotation of the object. The longer the pushing action is, the larger will be the error. While in the simulation, we can count on perfect localization, being able to use smaller thresholds for the navigation, on the real robot the localization has some drifts and inaccuracies that make these thresholds higher. However, thanks to the online updates of the push plans, the framework is still able to deal with these errors and continue to produce plans, completing the task. It can be also observed that there is no large

difference between simulation and real experiments, especially in terms of planning time.

Videos of the experiments can be found at this link.³

4.6. Comparison

Compared to [22] and [23] we were able to strongly extend the idea of a simulator-based push planner and use the framework on floating base robots. This adds the possibility of recovering autonomously from challenges that may impede and block the robot navigation, without the need of human intervention or to terminate the robot's mission. We added the possibility of including in the planning part the movements of the robot to check for feasibility, as well as the reshaping of the support polygon in the case of legged platforms. Furthermore, we incorporated a module to autonomously select the object to be pushed and sample a position that will be considered as a target location to move the object, increasing the autonomy introduced by the proposed framework. However, it is difficult to provide a more detailed comparison in terms of time or accuracy due to the strong differences between the platforms, tasks, objects moved, and overall distance moved. In fact, those methods do not take into account the possibility of moving the robot in space, therefore they move objects for shorter distances, which affects execution and planning times.

A possible method employed for comparison against the proposed pushing framework can be characterized by a simple approach in which the robot moves straight to the target without planning, pushing whatever is on its way to the goal. Such a method would work well in open spaces when there are no collisions with other objects. However, if the method is applied in constraint environments like corridors or corners, this approach will result in pushing the objects to the target location that has to be reached or it will anchor the objects to the other elements of the environment, making them unmovable and failing the task. Furthermore, when considering legged robots, it may be dangerous to drive toward objects without knowing what is in front of the robot because it could make the robot's legs collide with sharp or heavy objects, stressing or even damaging the actuators.

In the experiments carried out in this paper, the properties of the obstacles were known a priori and provided through a configuration file. In particular, the objects are simplified with rectangular shapes, resembling their bounding box, which can increase the pushing error in the case of irregular objects. However, this does not prevent the planner from finding a solution and completing the task. Instead, for

³ <https://youtu.be/8-QwRfkcKVQ>

what concerns the objects' poses, they were acquired using Aruco Markers since object segmentation and tracking were not the focus of the paper. Nevertheless, this assumption is reasonable since the output of an object segmentation module would provide estimates of the object properties, used by the proposed framework. Furthermore, thanks to the modularity of the designed framework, the object segmentation module can be easily and transparently changed with different software architectures to estimate the object's pose and properties from visual information, without the need to modify any other module of the framework. Finally, as mentioned in the previous Section, there is no need to have precise parameters for the mass and friction, since the execution is updated and the parameters are corrected during the execution.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we introduced a new framework that permits mobile robotic platforms to perform push planning of objects/obstacles and move them to new target locations. The pushing actions are planned using a simulation engine, to estimate the behavior of the object to be pushed, taking into account the physics of the push. Thanks to the Behavior Tree employed, the deviation between the planned and the actual object position is monitored enabling to replan the pushing action in case of large deviations. The results of the validation trials demonstrated that the proposed planner endows the mobile platforms with additional autonomous capabilities, effectively enabling them to exit or get unstuck from blocked navigation scenarios that prevent the robots from arriving to the target location. Future developments will target to realize object tracking and recognition modules that will permit to provide estimation of the 3D meshes of the objects, as well as their physical properties. Such information will be used to further refine the planning and replanning of the pushing actions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alessio De Luca: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Luca Muratore:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Nikos Tsagarakis:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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